

Phytochemical screening and Antimicrobial activity of honey bee (*Apis cerana indica*)-produced apiary honey against clinical strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*

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Abstract:

Honey made by honeybees (*Apis cerana indica*) and used in traditional medicines was tested for chemical components and antimicrobial activity. The phytochemical analysis of the honey (MPH) revealed the presence of resins, steroids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, saponification, protein, and saponins. The antimicrobial activity of honey (MPH) on fresh hospital isolates: *Staphylococcus aureus*-902, *E.coli*-443, *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* obtained at MTCC, Chandigarh, India was tested using the well diffusion method. The results demonstrate that *Cerana indica* honey has antimicrobial properties against *S. aureus*, *A. niger* and *C. albicans* but not against *E. coli*. The sample (MPH) exhibited the largest zone of inhibition (15.5 ± 0.7071) against *A. niger* at 20 mg/ml. Our findings demonstrate that honey, in addition to its role as a food additive and supplement, can be used as an effective and inexpensive source of antimicrobial agents for the treatment of bacterial and fungal illnesses.

Key words: Apiary, Honey, *Apis cerana indica*, antibacterial activity, antifungal activity, clinical isolates.

1. INTRODUCTION

Honey, a natural commodity with nutritional, economic, and environmental benefits, has been utilized in traditional medicine since prehistoric times (Eteraf-Oskouei and Najafi, 2013). Honey's quality is determined by its contents, which are primarily affected by bee species, nectar sources, geographical origin, and post-harvest processing. (Sousa *et al.*, 2016, Hossen *et al.*, 2017). The tropical nation of Indonesia is home to a wide variety of honey and honeybees. One of the native bee species that is frequently utilized

for traditional honey production is *Apis cerana* (Gratzer *et al.*, 2019).

Honey is a unique dietary product that contains beneficial substances from bees and plants. It contains phenolic acids, which have many biological effects and serve as natural antioxidants. Honey has peroxy-scavenging ability (Gheldof *et al.*, 2002). The use of beehive products for their pharmacological and therapeutic qualities is known as apitherapy. Although it is frequently referred to as an alternative treatment, something to consider as a last resort when all other options have been exhausted, increasing research on the topic is confirming its actual therapeutic efficacy (Weis *et al.*, 2022).

Plants have been used for healing since ancient times, making them as ubiquitous as medicine. Plants generally stimulate and augment the body's natural healing processes. They are the natural food source for humans. Throughout history, herbal treatments have been used to cure numerous infectious ailments. Plant materials continue to play an important role in primary health care as therapeutic treatments in many poor nations. The majority of the world's population continues to rely nearly entirely on plants for their pharmacological needs. Antimicrobial activity screening and phytochemical analysis of important plants have been of tremendous interest in the discovery of medications effective in the treatment of a variety of ailments (Ainslie, 1937).

Several *in vitro* investigations have revealed the antibacterial effects of honey (Lusby *et al.*, 2005; Kwakman *et al.*, 2008; Hassanain *et al.*, 2010), few have investigated the action against fungus. The incidence of fungal infections is increasing in both the community and hospital environments with numerous causal agents including yeasts, with *Candida* spp. being among the major species (Abi-Said *et al.*, 1997; Pfaller and Diekema, 2002) and filamentous fungi. Honey has been shown to have antifungal properties against *Candida albicans* yeast, as well as most species of *Aspergillus baumannii* and *Penicillium chrysogenum* (Willix *et al.*, 1992).

Antibiotic resistance against infections has prompted researchers to seek alternative cures. It is really of essential relevance to reveal new medicines directed at unique targets as developing alternatives to antibiotics, as well as confirmation of traditional remedies (Jenkins *et al.*, 2011). Its composition and quality vary widely depending on the botanical source of nectar, as well as environmental and climatic factors. Honey, depending on its quality, can improve human health and nutrition. Its therapeutic benefits are attributed to its antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and anti-oxidant properties. Interestingly, honey is increasingly becoming recognized as a complementary and alternative source of treatment in modern medicine. It is

active against both antibiotic-sensitive and antibiotic-resistant strains of microorganisms and has the ability to prevent the selection of additional resistant strains (Manyi-Loh *et al.*, 2011).

Researchers from all over the world have worked both *in vitro* and *in vivo* to spark the unknown benefits of the inestimable properties of honey and its applications (Irish *et al.*, 2008; Kumari *et al.*, 2010; Zaid *et al.*, 2010). In the modern day, the distinct biological, chemical, and physical features of honey have shown multiple benefit claims using various approaches. Honey is regarded in the scientific world as a sweetener, functional food, antioxidant, antibacterial, antiseptic, prebiotic, probiotic, immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, anti-tumour, and anti-cancer action, among other things (Jenkins *et al.*, 2011; Fauzi *et al.*, 2011).

The antibacterial properties of honey were initially documented in 1892 and are now well recognized. Honey has been used to treat and prevent wound infections since ancient times. Although honey is still utilized in many cultures, its clinical use in contemporary Western medicine was abandoned with the development of antibiotics. Globally, resistance is rising for all kinds of antibiotics, including the main last-resort medications (Walsh, 2003; Levy and Marshal, 2004); Even more concerning, few new antibiotics are being researched. The potency of honey against antibiotic-resistant microorganisms resulted in fresh interest in its application (Cooper *et al.*, 2002a; Cooper *et al.*, 2002b; Efem *et al.*, 1988).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Chemicals and Apparatus

All of the chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade purity. Ethanol, nutrient agar, Mueller–Hinton agar (MHA), and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased from Himedia (India). Other chemicals used in this experiment were of the highest quality and commercially available on the market. Gentamycin was also procured from Himedia (India). Throughout the media preparations and measurements, ultrapure water was used.

2.2. Collection of Honey Sample

Honey samples produced by *Cerana indica* bees were obtained from honeybee colonies in Annamalai Nagar region in the year of 2023. The samples were stored in the refrigerated in airtight plastic containers until analysis.

2.3. Phytochemical quality analysis

The honey (MPH) was submitted to qualitative analysis to identify its compounds, including alkaloids, saponins, tannins, flavonoids, resin, steroids, proteins, and carbohydrates, using normal methods. (Harborne, 1998; Gul *et al.*, 2017).

2.4. Antibacterial screening of honey

The antibacterial activity of honey was determined using the agar well diffusion method (Dhilna *et al.*, 2020). After sterilization at 121°C for 25 minutes, all selected bacterial colonies were sub cultured in Nutrient Agar Media 2 (NAM) with a pH of 7. To make the agar slants, approximately 4 ml of NAM was added to test tubes, which were then incubated overnight at 37°C. Tubes containing 20 ml of MHA were injected with newly prepared bacterial inoculums through a sterile loop to ensure equal dispersion. The pre-inoculated media was placed into Petri plates and allowed to set before cutting 8 mm wells with a sterile cork borer. (*Staphylococcus aureus*-902 and *E.coli*-443) Wells were cut and concentration of sample MPH (20, 15, 10 and 5 mg/ml) was added and an equivalent volume of DMSO as a negative control. After standing for 30 minutes to allow for pre-diffusion of the extract into the medium, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 16-20 hours. The inhibitory zones on the plates were analysed and compared to a positive control with gentamycin. All experiments were performed in triplicate, and average values were obtained.

2.5. Antifungal screening of honey

The potato dextrose agar medium was prepared by dissolving 20 grams of potato infusion, 2 grams of dextrose, and 1.5 grams of agar in 100 ml of distilled water. The mixture was autoclaved at 15 lbs pressure at 121°C for 15 minutes. Once sterilized,

the medium was poured into 100mm petri plates (25-30 ml per plate) while still in a molten state. Petri plates containing 20 ml of potato dextrose agar medium were inoculated with a 72-hour culture of the fungal strains *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*. Wells were cut into the agar, and varying concentrations of the sample MPH (20, 15, 10, and 5 mg/ml) were added to each well. The plates were then incubated at 28°C for 72 hours. The antifungal activity was assessed by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zones around the wells. Amphotericin B served as a positive control. All experiments were performed in triplicate, and average values were obtained. The results were analysed using GraphPad Prism 6.0 software (USA).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Qualitative phytochemical screening

The honey sample (MPH) required phytochemical analysis and was discovered to include bioactive components such as resins, steroids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, saponification, protein, and saponins. The degree of colour change is a qualitative assessment of the amount of each chemical present in the MPH sample, given in Table 1 by the number of plus signs (+).

Table 1. Showing the qualitative phytochemical screening methods

S.No.	Name of the Sample	Phytochemical compound	Result
1.	MPH	Resins	+
2.		Carboxylic acid	-
3.		Tannins	-
4.		Steroids	+
5.		Flavonoid	+
6.		Carbohydrates	+
7.		Glycosides	-
8.		Saponification	+
9.		Protein	+
10.		Phenol	-
11.		Biuret	-
12.		Soponin	+
13.		Gum	-
14.		Flavanoglycosides	-
15.		Alkaloids	-

Sample; + : present, - : absent.

3.2. Antibacterial Activity

The results of antibacterial screening are reported in Fig 1,2 and Table 2. The sample demonstrated antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, with a maximum zone of inhibition of 15.5 ± 0.7071 at 20 mg/ml, but no inhibition on *E. coli*.

Fig. 1 Effect of sample MPH against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Fig 2. Effect of sample MPH against *E.coli*.

Table 2. Means \pm SD of zone of inhibition obtained by sample MPH against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E.coli*.

S. No	Name of the test organism	Name of the test sample	Zone of inhibition (mm)				
			Mean \pm SD				
			20 mg/ml	15 mg/ml	10 mg/ml	5 mg/ml	PC
1.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	MPH	4.5 \pm 0.707	3.25 \pm 0.35	0	0	16.75 \pm 1.06
2.	<i>E. coli</i>		0	0	0	0	15.5 \pm 0.7

SD – Standard Deviation, *Significance - $p < 0.05$

3.3. Antifungal Activity

The results of antifungal screening are reported in Fig 3,4 and Table 3. The sample demonstrated antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*. The highest zone of inhibition against *Aspergillus niger* (15.5 \pm 0.7071) at 20 mg/ml.

Fig 3. Effect of sample MPH against *Aspergillus niger*.

Fig 4. Effect of sample MPH against *Candida albicans*.

Table 3. SD± Means of zone of inhibition obtained by sample MPH against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*.

S.NO	Name of the test organism	Name of the test sample	Zone of inhibition (mm) SD ± Mean				
			20 mg/ml	15 mg/ml	10 mg/ml	5 mg/ml	PC
1.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	MPH	15.5±0.7071	11.35±0.49	0	0	16.5±0.7071
2.	<i>Candida albicans</i>		14.45±0.63	0	0	0	16.75±1.06

SD – Standard Deviation, *Significance - p< 0.05

4. DISCUSSION

The phytochemical analysis of honey in Table 1 shows that resins, steroids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, saponification, protein, and saponins are present in the honey examined. These families of chemicals have been shown to have therapeutic activity against a variety of pathogens, which supports their historic use in disease treatment. Saponins in honey have been discovered to be an antibacterial material on the cell wall of numerous species (Harborne, 1998).

The results of the well diffusion test, as shown in Tables 2 and 3, revealed that the honey sample possesses antibacterial and antifungal properties. This suggests that honey may be a treatment for disorders caused by *S. aureus*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Candida albicans*. Similarly, previous work has shown that honey has been used to heal recalcitrant wounds, and it was found to be effective in vitro against a wide range of multi-resistant organisms, including methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), vancomycin-resistant *Enterococci* (VRE), and multiresistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Cooper et al., 2002; George and Cutting, 2007).

Since the flora source determines many of the honey's characteristics, such as its flavour, aroma, colour, and composition, the difference in the antimicrobial potential of the honey used in this study compared to earlier studies suggests that the source of the nectar may have contributed to the variation in the antimicrobial activities of honey. Specifically, the flowers from which bees collected nectar to produce the honey Mogessie (1994). The variance could also be related to differences in pathogen growth rate, dietary requirements, temperature, inoculum size, and the test procedures themselves. (Gaill and Jon, 1995).

5. Conclusion

This work has shown that apiary honey produced by *C. indica* has antimicrobial activity when tested. Moreover, the pharmacological, standardization and clinical evaluation on the effect of honey are essential before using it as a preventive and curative measure to common diseases related to the test organisms. Therefore, the antimicrobial activity of honey produced by *C. indica* against clinical microbial isolates indicates the usefulness of the honey in clinical practice against both antifungal and antibacterial infections. According to the current study, honey can function as an antifungal antimicrobial agent more effectively than an antibacterial agent.

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